
The impact of authentic materials (news articles, essays, podcasts) on reading motivation and reading comprehension in 9th-grade EFL students

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Annotation

This article examines the role of authentic materials in teaching reading to ninth-grade students in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms. Authentic materials, such as newspapers, magazines, online articles, advertisements, and short stories created for real-life communication, are believed to make language learning more meaningful and engaging for learners. The study focuses on how these materials influence students' reading motivation, comprehension abilities, and overall interest in reading activities. Through classroom observations, reading tasks, and learner feedback, the research evaluates whether authentic texts encourage students to participate more actively in lessons and develop better reading strategies. The findings suggest that exposure to real-world language increases learners' confidence, enriches vocabulary acquisition, and improves their ability to understand contextual meaning. In addition, authentic materials help create a more interactive and learner-centered environment, promoting critical thinking and communication skills. The article concludes that integrating authentic resources into reading instruction can significantly support both language development and long-term reading engagement among ninth-grade EFL students.

Keywords

Authentic materials, reading motivation, ninth grade, EFL, reading comprehension, self-efficacy, Bloom's Taxonomy, Reflective reading, Foundational reading, Analytical reading, Self-Determination theory, Achievement Goal theory, Social Cognitive theory, intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation

9-sinf EFL o'quvchilarida o'qish motivatsiyasi va tushunishga haqiqiy materiallar (yangiliklar, maqolalar, podkastlar)ning ta'siri

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini xorijiy til sifatida o'rganayotgan (EFL) to'qqizinchi sinf o'quvchilariga o'qish ko'nikmalarini o'rgatishda autentik materiallarning o'rni tahlil qilinadi. Gazetalar, jurnallar, onlayn maqolalar, reklama matnlari va qisqa hikoyalar

kabi real hayotiy muloqot uchun yaratilgan autentik materiallar til o'rganish jarayonini o'quvchilar uchun yanada mazmunli va qiziqarli qiladi. Tadqiqot ushbu materiallarning o'quvchilarning o'qishga bo'lgan motivatsiyasi, matnni tushunish qobiliyati hamda o'qishga bo'lgan umumiy qiziqishiga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishini o'rganishga qaratilgan. Sinf kuzatuvlari, o'qish topshiriqlari va o'quvchilarning fikr-mulohazalari orqali autentik matnlarning darslarda faol ishtirok etishga va samarali o'qish strategiyalarini rivojlantirishga yordam berishi baholanadi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, real til materiallaridan foydalanish o'quvchilarning ishonchini oshiradi, lug'at boyligini kengaytiradi va matnning kontekstual ma'nosini tushunishni yaxshilaydi. Bundan tashqari, autentik materiallar tanqidiy fikrlash va kommunikativ ko'nikmalarni rivojlantiruvchi, o'quvchiga yo'naltirilgan interaktiv ta'lim muhitini yaratishga yordam beradi. Xulosa qilib aytganda, o'qish darslarida autentik resurslardan foydalanish to'qqizinchi sinf EFL o'quvchilarining til rivoji va o'qishga bo'lgan barqaror qiziqishini sezilarli darajada qo'llab-quvvatlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar *Autentik materiallar, o'qish motivatsiyasi, to'qqizinchi sinf, chet tili sifatida ingliz tili, o'qishni tushunish, o'ziga ishonch, Bloom taksonomiyasi, reflektiv o'qish, boshlang'ich o'qish, analitik o'qish, o'zini o'zi belgilash nazariyasi, yutuq maqsadlari nazariyasi, ijtimoiy-kognitiv nazariya, ichki motivatsiya, tashqi motivatsiya*

Влияние аутентичных материалов (новостей, статей, подкастов) на мотивацию к чтению и понимание прочитанного у учащихся 9-го класса, изучающих английский как иностранный язык

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Аннотация *В данной статье рассматривается роль аутентичных материалов в обучении чтению учащихся девярых классов в условиях преподавания английского языка как иностранного (EFL). Аутентичные материалы, такие как газеты, журналы, онлайн-статьи, рекламные объявления и короткие рассказы, созданные для реального общения, делают процесс изучения языка более значимым и интересным для учащихся. Исследование сосредоточено на том, как данные материалы влияют на мотивацию к чтению, развитие навыков понимания текста и общий интерес школьников к чтению. С помощью наблюдений на уроках, заданий по чтению и отзывов учащихся оценивается, способствуют ли аутентичные тексты более активному участию в занятиях и развитию эффективных стратегий чтения. Результаты показывают, что использование реальных языковых материалов повышает уверенность учащихся, расширяет словарный запас и улучшает понимание контекстуального значения текста. Кроме того,*

аутентичные материалы помогают создать более интерактивную и ориентированную на ученика образовательную среду, развивая критическое мышление и коммуникативные навыки. В заключение отмечается, что интеграция аутентичных ресурсов в обучение чтению значительно способствует языковому развитию и формированию устойчивого интереса к чтению у учащихся девятого класса.

Ключевые слова

Аутентичные материалы, мотивация к чтению, девятый класс, английский как иностранный, понимание прочитанного, самооффективность, Таксономия Блума, базовое чтение, аналитическое чтение, рефлексивное чтение, теория самодетерминации, теория целевых достижений, социально-когнитивная теория, внутренняя мотивация, внешняя мотивация

Introduction

In today's modern world, the rapid development of technology, media and social networks is creating favourable conditions for people to communicate, regardless of their national language or social background. Not only communication, but also the development of business, trade and science is providing a stimulus for this. Indeed, this development and the desire to communicate are further increasing people's need to learn languages.

The process of learning a language requires time and skill from learners. And in this process, four main skills are required: reading, listening, speaking and writing. Students who can combine these skills can achieve results quickly. Among all these skills, we consider that the most effective is the ability to read, because with this skill, people can acquire the necessary knowledge, by absorbing this knowledge, students have the opportunity to improve their other skills as well.

Reading is a process of decoding, comprehension, fluency and also analyzing received information. Because it starts from decoding letter or signs that helps comprehension and later analyzing and memorizing what is read. According to Valenzuela and Janovsky (2023), reading has tremendous benefits for brain function such as,

solving problems or making decision, so the readers have purpose to learn something new, to write stories, essays and poems.

This is how educational researchers answer the question of what reading actually is as a skill. According to Diane Henry Leipzig (2001), reading is not a simple process but a multi-functional one. It comprises the ability to read and understanding written text. In this regard, we believe that reading is not merely a mechanical activity but a sophisticated process of meaning construction. Therefore, it involves multiple interrelated functions, including the ability to decode written symbols such as letters and signs, as well as to understand and analyze the meaning conveyed through text.

Frances A. Connors (2003) also made a similar remark. We consider that because reading is a cognitive process, it involves extracting meaning from print, as well as understanding that meaning, retaining it and linking it to existing knowledge.

Similarly, in "Reading" (2018), the author defines reading as a process and linguistic activity that encompasses phonemic awareness, decoding, text comprehension and metacognitive skills. This means that reading is not a simple, one-way process but, by integrating multiple functions, can have a positive effect on the reader. Therefore, for

successful reading and to fully master this process, the reader must also apply these functions in practice. These functions are the step-by-step components of the reading process, encompassing decoding, fluency, comprehension, vocabulary, critical reading and metacognitive skills.

Methodology

These reading components are closely interlinked and complementary, further strengthening the learner's reading process. First and foremost, the reading process involves decoding – recognising letters and reading words, and this process serves as the foundation. Without decoding, it would be impossible to read any text.

After decoding, the next stage is fluency, the ability to read faster and smoother. Fluent readers do not pay attention to decode letters or do not stop while reading, as they know all letters, and connect them into words and sentences. Difficulty in decoding can cause losing motivation and not fully understanding overall meaning from the text. Fluency paves the way for the next stage, Vocabulary.

For this, the Vocabulary Knowledge function is also important. Without knowing the vocabulary it might be difficult to understand meaning in the text. For that reason every learner should start reading process by learning a lot of vocabulary in pre-stage. However human brain is not a computer. It can restore only important and relevant information such as new vocabularies. Most scientist worked on to find out how to learn more vocabulary faster and effective, so that these words can last longer and permanent in people's memory. For instance, Stuart Webb&Paul Nation (2017) explained how to boost vocabulary knowledge and the role of it in second language acquisition. They highlighted that without knowing proper amount of vocabulary to become fluent in second language learning is impossible Because it serves as a foundation for language acquisition. According to the authors Stuart Webb&Paul Nation, each learner should know

more than thousands of words (8,000-9,000 words and their way of usage) to read and understand the whole meaning. Having strong dictionary means having great opportunity to understanding the text.

According to Meganathan, P.M., Yap, N.T., Paramasivam, S., & Jalaluddin, I. (2019; 51-67) there are two ways of learning vocabulary. They are Intentional and Incidental ways of acquiring vocabulary knowledge. We believe that students who can combine these two ways and use both of them in vocabulary learning would really get more benefit.

Intentional learning means learning vocabulary deliberately using flashcards, vocabulary exercises, making sentences and stories or making list of new vocabularies and repeat them frequently. With the help of these learning tools, students can learn vocabulary intentional.

The second way is Incidental vocabulary learning. Students learn vocabulary naturally without flashcards or list of words. For example, by reading books and stories, watching movies or listening to podcasts. Students naturally learn new words and phrases in the real context. This way of learning takes long time and active engagement is crucial.

Repetition is also very effective and important way of learning and remembering new words. Stuart Webb&Paul Nation (2017) said that, frequent encountering word, such as 10- 15 times can really help memory to remember these words easily and long time. Webb and Nation explained that to see the words frequently and different context, learners should read extensively. It means they read books, magazines or scientific articles and encounter their previous learned vocabulary. This type of constant exposure for reading extensively is coincides with Incidental vocabulary learning which means learning vocabulary naturally. Learning high- frequency words is also one of the critical way of learning new vocabulary and being fluent reader.

Comprehension is understanding the meaning of the text and linking it to existing

information in the brain. We consider that Reading should not be viewed solely as the mechanical decoding of letters and sounds. Once readers acquire basic phonological awareness, they must also develop the ability to connect textual information with their existing knowledge and to analyze meaning at a deeper cognitive level. Limiting reading to surface-level decoding reduces it to a mechanical activity; however, human cognition is far more complex. It involves continuous mental development, the formation of neural connections, and the capacity for imagination, all of which contribute to deeper comprehension and critical engagement with texts.

And at the highest level, Critical Reading and Metacognitive strategies are implemented. The reason they occupy the highest tier is that they enable students to carry out complex tasks such as analysis, finding answers to critical questions, thinking logically, and achieving a deep understanding of the subject's essence. As students perform these functions sequentially and in a coordinated manner, their reading skills will be elevated to a high level.

Critical Reading differs from basic Reading and understanding the information. Terry Heick (2022) mentioned that the process of Critical Reading mainly involves comprehension of text's idea, audience, gist, arguments and implicit meaning. This process is not only understanding what is written on the page, but also comprehension of true essence and purpose of the writing.

According to Roman Taraban (2019), effective reading primarily relies on metacognitive reading processes. Because this process improves reading comprehension, critical reading and academic achievement. Metacognitive reading skills are techniques that successful readers can actively control their comprehension by using different strategies based on the text and language.

The reading process is not just about understanding the text. It is also important to retain the information for a long time. When

solving complex cognitive tasks, student also relies on stored knowledge, and the processes of analysis and synthesis are themselves linked to retaining information in memory. Using strategies makes it much easier to recall this knowledge.

According to Christine Nuttall (1982-2005), how a reader understands a text depends on their knowledge, vocabulary and the complexity of the text. Therefore, this is an active process, and the knowledge retained in the reader's memory is not always complete, because the capacity for understanding varies according to the reader's abilities and also depends on their knowledge and experience. For this reason, the learner's expanding vocabulary and knowledge, as well as their worldview, help them to understand the text more easily.

Nuttall (2005), in his book *Teaching Reading Skills in a Foreign Language* the most important reading strategies have been outlined. These strategies include: scanning, skimming, prediction, questioning, inferring and summarising.

Scanning helps to locate specific information, such as dates, names and facts. This strategy is based on finding the necessary information quickly in a short period of time. Skimming, by contrast, is about reading rapidly to grasp the overall meaning of a text. Also, Prediction is the process of using keywords or a headline to infer what a text is about, thereby helping to capture interest and attention. In the next stage we can use Questioning which is reading the text, asking oneself questions and prompting a deeper understanding of the text, whereas inferring is uncovering the hidden idea. And one of the most effective strategies is final summarising, which involves reading the text and retelling it which helps the student to remember the topic.

Bloom's Taxonomy and its application in teaching Reading skills

In contemporary world, the education system is highly demanding higher-level thinking skills such as creativity, analyzing,

evaluating skills. For that reason, prominent pedagogical psychologist Benjamin Bloom's pedagogical framework became popular in educational system. The framework offers structured division of each level starting from low-level to the highest level to provide step-by-step improvement, so the teachers can apply this readily framework and design their lessons according to this framework properly and confidently.

Bloom's Taxonomy was originally presented by Benjamin Bloom and his team of pedagogical psychologists in 1956. It was given in the book "Taxonomy of Educational Objectives (1956)", which provides this framework in hierarchical order of each objectives and goals of education. The aim of the Taxonomy is that, to create model of common teaching objectives that teachers can share and discuss with each other, create effective lesson planning and assessment methods.

As the teaching theories and systems changed over time, the Bloom's Taxonomy was also renovated in 2001 by Lorin Anderson and David Krathwohl. The role of Bloom's

Taxonomy in teaching Reading skills is crucial. Because Reading is not passive, but active cognitive skill that requires several skills such as decoding letters, understanding meaning and critical thinking is important. Applying Bloom's Taxonomy in teaching reading is the effective way that allows teachers to follow the single model that can guide to the right direction.

The original taxonomy included three domains: Cognitive (knowledge), Affective (emotional development) and Psychomotor (physical skills).

Cognitive domain is mostly used in academic studies, because it is related directly to this sphere. This domain includes intellectual processes such as, receiving the knowledge, applying in real world and analyzing and creating by using this knowledge. Benjamin Bloom (1956), explains that cognitive domain consisted of levels that each level requires cognitive skills, thinking deeply and mental ability.

Cognitive domain have six levels starting from low-level thinking to high-level thinking skills.

№	Types	Definitions
1	<i>Remembering</i>	It is the first core level of Cognitive domain that requires active recalling of knowledge which is previously learned. Teacher make students to remember facts, numbers, years, characters of the story for better memorization. In this order, students do not need to understand the meaning. They should only memorize facts and data to remember. This is the important level in reading comprehension.
2	<i>Understanding</i>	The ability, to understand the meaning of a paragraph or an entire text and to explain what it is about.
3	<i>Applying</i>	The ability to apply newly acquired information in real life and in various situations, or to use it to solve a problem.
4	<i>Analyzing</i>	The ability to understand the meaning of a text and its interconnectedness by studying it in sections, and to compare the author's purpose and ideas with other sources.
5	<i>Evaluating</i>	The ability to make judgement a text after analysing it, based on evidence and reasoning. At this level, it is assessed by evaluating the text's credibility and whether or not one agrees with the author's argument.

6	<i>Creating</i>	the ability to create new products, ideas or personal opinions and to draw conclusions based on acquired knowledge. Examples of this include writing the ending of a story, drawing conclusions, and expressing one's opinion in writing or orally.
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Table 1. *Levels of Cognitive Domain of Bloom's Taxonomy 2001*

At the lowest levels, students focus on recalling knowledge and understanding it. The advantage of this strategy is that without going through such simple stages, one cannot learn to read, and this strategy serves as the foundation. However, at this stage the knowledge acquired is more superficial, does not require deep study, and focuses not on understanding the content but merely on rote memorisation. For instance, students can memorise 10 vocabulary items by using flashcards or match them with definition that can help them to remember new words.

In Understanding level of Taxonomy students construct meaning from the texts (written or spoken), graphs or from communication. For example, students read a short article about climate change and rewrite the article with their own words.

Applying acquired knowledge in practice takes place during the applying stage and paves the way for significant milestones. In other words, it encompasses high-level genuine critical thinking, analytical skills and the like. To apply the knowledge students do real life tasks, such as, calculating the cost of grocery list.

Analyzing is breaking the text down into sections for analysis and drawing conclusions. Activity to use analyzing: students read two advertisement from magazine and create Venn diagram by analyzing differences of these articles.

Evaluating is the ability to make judgements and critique according to the existing criteria. Student can review classmate's essay and give judgement based on the rubrics to analyze whether the opinion of writer is true.

Creating – new ideas and principles that, while complex, when applied not only satisfy

existing knowledge but also allow it to be analysed, to check its accuracy, as well as to devise new ideas, solve the problem, and so on. Example activity: Students work with groups to make water collecting system from rain by using recycled materials. This activity improves students' creative ability.

Foundational, Analytical and Reflective Reading Instruction Based on Integration of Reading Components and Bloom's Cognitive Domains

One of the most exciting discoveries in my study about reading instruction is the integration of the three important phases which are Foundational, Analytical, and Reflective Reading. I think these phases really shows how reading can develop from simple understanding into deeper thinking and personal reflection. The foundational phase help students to build important skills like vocabulary, fluency and comprehension, which creates a strong base for learning. Also, the analytical phase encourages learners to think more critically by analyzing ideas, identifying meanings and evaluating information in the text. Finally, the reflective phase allows students connects reading with their own experiences, express their opinions and create new ideas. What makes this integration very effective is because it combines reading components with Bloom's Cognitive Domains in a natural progression from remembering and understanding to evaluating and creating. In my opinion, this approach is very powerful since it not only improves reading abilities, but also develop independent, critical and thoughtful learners who can apply their knowledge both in classroom and outside of it.

Figure 1. Levels of Cognitive Domain in Bloom's Taxonomy (2001)

The components of reading: decoding, fluency, vocabulary knowledge, comprehension, critical reading and metacognitive reading skills can be aligned progressively with the Revised Bloom's

Taxonomy (2001) to create effective and clear teaching framework for teachers by integrating linguistic and cognitive dimensions of reading process. (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Three-Phase Reading Instruction

From a pedagogical perspective, focusing only on lower-levels leads to poor understanding and memorization. In contrast, applying high-levels encourages better retention of knowledge, creative thinking and deeper learning.

Applying the levels as a model in planning lessons is very effective, especially in teaching reading skills to EFL classes. Using strategies according to these levels and creating meaningful activities defining this model can increase motivation and creativity. This domain also plays a crucial role in reading comprehension and better application of knowledge in real life, increasing curiosity and motivation.

On the other hand, teaching or motivating learners of ESL is one of the main challenges for educators. By further enhancing reading ability and promoting top-down, reading components and Bloom's taxonomy in the teaching process, educators have been striving to develop students' critical thinking skills to meet the demands of the modern world. This is because it is known that students' enthusiasm and interest in reading have been waning recently.

According to statistics from the National Literacy Trust (2024), only 34.6% of young people expressed an interest in reading in research conducted since 2025, and 20.5% read a book every day. It can be concluded that traditional methods and approaches are no longer effective in boosting students' interest. Because of the main time-consuming and distracting factors for students, particularly the increasing time spent on mass media and social networks, and the growing tendency to seek information not from books but from video platforms, are causing reading skills to decline. For students, overcoming these problems and increasing their interest and motivation in reading begins with understanding what motivation is.

It is acknowledged in modern research that an increase in reading motivation is multidimensional, encompassing both external

(extrinsic) and internal (intrinsic) elements, which influence the reader in an integrated manner (Guthrie, 2021). Distinguishing these elements highlights the importance of considering the materials through which a learner is influenced. Intrinsic motivation is a motivation that is linked not to the activity itself, but to the participant in the process, arising primarily from curiosity and a strong innate interest. With this type of motivation, the learner persists with determination, continuing long and difficult learning processes without interruption (Belet Boyacı & Güner, 2018).

Extrinsic motivation, on the other hand, relies primarily on external factors. That is, motivation is tied to external incentives, such as top marks, motivational rewards or public recognition. Research shows that relying on external motivation is a short-term process. Intrinsic motivation is the primary factor that continually sustains the motivation to study (Deci & Ryan, 2020).

This multifaceted structure of learning motivation has also been confirmed by scientific research. Neugebauer and Fujimoto (2020) analyzed three instruments used to measure learning motivation in 222 high school students and identified different but interrelated factors using item response theory. The results showed that although there are differences between the concepts based on self-determination theory, social-cognitive approach, and expectancy-value theory, they converge in some aspects, especially in the views related to a sense of competence and social motivation. This indicates the need to understand learning motivation not as a single simple factor, but as a system of interrelated views and attitudes.

Four major theoretical approaches play an important role in understanding motivation to learn: self-determination theory, expectancy-value theory, social cognitive theory, and achievement goal theory. Taboada Barber, Levush, and Lutz Klaua (2018) apply these theories to the process of teaching

literacy, noting that each of them sheds light on how the learning environment affects motivation from different perspectives.

Three-Phase Reading Instruction integrated with Motivation theories

We believe that the three reading phases are closely connected with major motivation theories because each phase supports different motivational needs of learners. In the Literal Reading Phase, which mainly focuses on decoding, fluency, and basic vocabulary knowledge, the principles of Cognitive-Behavior Theory are important since students usually develop motivation through repetition, reinforcement, teacher feedback, and successful reading experiences. At this stage, learners often need more support and encouragement from the teacher. For Grade 9 students, possible activities can include vocabulary matching tasks, pronunciation practice, guided reading, repeated reading, identifying key words in the text, and answering simple WH-questions. Sometimes students may still struggle with unfamiliar words or read too slowly, so these activities help them become more confident reader.

As learners move to the Analytical Reading Phase, they begin to apply and analyze information through comprehension and interpretation activities. This phase is strongly related to Expectancy-Value Theory, because students are usually more motivated when they

feel that they can complete the task successfully and when the reading topic seems useful or interesting for them. Suitable activities for Grade 9 learners include identifying the main idea, making inferences, sequencing events, comparing characters, completing graphic organizers, and discussing “why” or “how” questions. However, some students may lose concentration during longer texts or have difficulty explaining their ideas clearly, especially when the text is complex.

Finally, the Critical-Reflective Reading Phase connects with Self-Determination Theory and Achievement Goal Theory, because students are expected to read more independently, evaluate ideas, and reflect on their own understanding. In this phase, motivation increases through autonomy, self-expression, and mastery goals. Appropriate Grade 9 activities may include debating the author’s opinion, evaluating arguments, writing reflective journals, creating alternative endings, and participating in group discussions. Even though students become more independent at this level, they sometimes hesitate to express their opinions or feel unsure about giving critical responses. Therefore, the progression from lower to higher reading phases not only develops students’ cognitive reading skills, but also gradually improves their confidence, motivation, and engagement in reading activities. (Figure 3)

Figure 3. *Three-Phase Reading framework with Motivation theories*

9th-grade is a critical period in the study of reading motivation, as it is a period of significant developmental change and is often characterized by a decline in interest in reading. Guthrie and Wigfield (2018) found that intrinsic reading motivation gradually declines during the middle school years, with a particularly pronounced decline between grades 7 and 9. This is concerning because advanced reading skills are essential for success in all subjects in the upper grades. There are several factors that contribute to the decline in motivation during adolescence.

First, the complexity of the learning materials often exceeds the reading level of students, which can lead to them struggling and avoiding reading altogether (Rizqon, Andreani, & Astuti, 2021). Second, the freedom of choice given to students during the transition from primary to secondary education decreases, which weakens their interest in independent learning which is a big problem. Third, during the process of forming adolescents social identities, they may perceive reading as a less attractive activity or as an activity that does not correspond to their interests (Moje, 2018).

However, research also shows that a decline in motivation is not inevitable. Some effective teaching methods have been found to help maintain or even increase interest in reading during adolescence. These include allowing students to choose their reading materials, connecting texts to their interests and life experiences, organizing social interactions around the texts they read, and creating a sense of achievement through texts that are appropriate to their level but still somewhat challenging (Guthrie et al., 2021; Belet Boyacı & Güner, 2018). So basically, there are ways to fix this problem.

The concept of authenticity in language teaching has evolved significantly since the era of the communicative language teaching approach in the 1970s and 1980s. In its original meaning, authenticity refers to the extent to which materials correspond to real-life

language use, that is, they are close to real communicative situations, as opposed to texts artificially created specifically for educational purposes.

One widely used definition is given by Peacock (2017), who defines authentic materials as "materials produced to serve a specific social purpose within a language community." This definition implies that such materials are not produced for language learners, but for real communication between native speakers. Examples include newspapers and magazines, advertisements, websites, social media posts, menus, brochures, films, television programs, and podcasts and etc.

However, the concept of authenticity is not so simple and there are different views around it. As Lewis Lansford notes (2024), experts have long debated whether materials can still be considered authentic after they have been adapted for pedagogical purposes. Some scholars distinguish between "authentic texts" which are unmodified and "semi-authentic texts" that are adapted for learners.

Gilmore (2019) argues that authenticity is not a characteristic of the text itself, but rather a phenomenon that is formed in the process of interaction between the text, the reader, and the task.

In this analysis, authentic materials are understood as texts or other types of media that were originally created for non-educational, real-life purposes and that retain their essential characteristics when used in the language teaching process. This definition includes printed materials like newspapers, magazines, booklets as well as audio-visual materials such as videos, podcasts, social media content and etc.

Authentic materials can be classified according to various criteria. Setyowati & Sukmawan (2019) propose dividing them into three groups based on the form of transmission which are printed materials, audio materials, and visual materials. Printed authentic materials include newspapers and magazines, brochures, menus, advertisements, letters,

emails, and social media posts. Audio authentic materials include podcasts, radio broadcasts, songs, and recorded conversations. Visual authentic materials include photographs, infographics, videos, and films.

Authentic materials are also classified according to genre and purpose, especially in the process of teaching reading. Berardo (2021) distinguishes the following types.

№	Types	Examples
1	<i>Informational texts</i>	newspapers, magazines, encyclopedias, and websites – mainly serve to convey information
2	<i>Instructional texts</i>	manuals, recipes, various instructions – are written to explain a process or action
3	<i>Persuasive texts</i>	advertisements, opinion articles, reviews – are aimed at influencing the reader's view or behavior
4	<i>Fictional (narrative) texts</i>	short stories, novels, personal stories – are created to interest the reader or evoke an emotional impact
5	<i>Transactional (transactional) texts</i>	letters, emails, various forms – serve to communicate or carry out daily practical tasks

Table 2. *Authentic materials according to genre and purpose*

This genre-based classification is particularly relevant for 9th grade teaching because the Common Core State Standards and similar educational standards emphasize the importance of presenting students with a variety of text types within different subject areas which is very important.

Understanding the difference between authentic and constructed or pedagogical materials is important in assessing the specific contribution of authentic materials to reading motivation. Constructed materials are texts specifically designed for language learners, typically featuring limited vocabulary, simplified syntactic structure, and a gradual placement of grammatical units (Fitria, 2022).

Both types have their own advantages. The materials created provide systematic, step-by-step teaching of language features, guarantee comprehensibility appropriate to the specific language level of the students, and allow for the practice of targeted grammatical or lexical units. However, some critics believe

that such materials often lack the naturalness, relevance, and true communicative purpose inherent in authentic texts (Rama, 2020).

Conclusion

In conclusion, this article has demonstrated that authentic materials are a theoretically grounded and empirically supported instructional approach for enhancing reading motivation among 9th-grade learners. The combination of theoretical frameworks such as self-determination theory, expectancy-value theory, and social cognitive theory together with empirical evidence from quasi-experimental studies, classroom action research and survey research give strong support for motivational benefits of authentic materials. Finally, authentic materials are an activity-based approach applicable to EFL classrooms that would greatly benefit not only the linguistic aspect but also equip students for the internalization of real-world reading habits and lifelong learning which is why it is highly recommended.

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